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Efail: Breaking S/MIME and OpenPGP Email Encryption using Exfiltration Channels

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Abstract

OpenPGP and S/MIME are the two prime standards for providing end-to-end security for emails. We describe novel attacks built upon a technique we call *malleability gadgets* to reveal the plaintext of encrypted emails. We use CBC/CFB gadgets to inject malicious plaintext snippets into encrypted emails. These snippets abuse existing and standard conforming backchannels to exfiltrate the full plaintext after decryption. We describe malleability gadgets for emails using HTML, CSS, and X.509 functionality. The attack works for emails even if they were collected long ago, and it is triggered as soon as the recipient decrypts a single maliciously crafted email from the attacker.

We devise working attacks for both OpenPGP and S/MIME encryption, and show that exfiltration channels exist for 23 of the 35 tested S/MIME email clients and 10 of the 28 tested OpenPGP email clients. While it is advisable to update the OpenPGP and S/MIME standards to fix these vulnerabilities, some clients had even more severe implementation flaws allowing straightforward exfiltration of the plaintext.

1 Introduction

Despite the emergence of many secure messaging technologies, email is still one of the most common methods to exchange information and data, reaching 269 billion messages per day in 2017 [1].

While transport security between mail servers is useful against some attacker scenarios, it does not offer reliable security guarantees regarding confidentiality and authenticity of emails. Reports of pervasive data collection efforts by nation state actors, large-scale breaches of email servers, revealing millions of email messages [2–5], or attackers compromising email accounts to search the emails for valuable data [6, 7] underline that transport security alone is not sufficient. End-to-end encryption

is designed to protect user data in such scenarios. With end-to-end encryption, the email infrastructure becomes merely a transportation service for opaque email data and no compromise – aside from the endpoints of sender or receiver – should affect the security of an end-to-end encrypted email.

S/MIME and OpenPGP. The two most prominent standards offering end-to-end encryption for email, S/MIME (Secure / Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions) and OpenPGP (Pretty Good Privacy), co-exist for more than two decades now. Although the cryptographic security of them was subject to criticism [8–10], little was published about practical attacks. Instead, S/MIME is commonly used in corporate and government environments.¹ It benefits from its ability to integrate into PKIs and that most widely-used email clients support it by default. OpenPGP often requires the installation of additional software and, besides a steady userbase within the technical community, is recommended for people in high-risk environments. In fact, human rights organizations such as Amnesty International [11], EFF [12], or Reporters without Borders [13] recommend using PGP.

We show that this trust is not justified, neither in S/MIME nor in OpenPGP. Based on the complexity of these two specifications and usage of obsolete cryptographic primitives, we introduce two novel attacks.

Backchannels and exfiltration channels. One of the basic building blocks for our attacks are backchannels. A backchannel is any functionality that interacts with the network, for example, a method for forcing the email client to invoke an external URL. A simple example uses an HTML image tag `` which forces the email client to download an image from `efail.de`. These backchannels are widely known for their privacy im-

¹A comprehensive list of European companies and agencies supporting S/MIME is available at <https://gist.github.com/rmoriz/5945400>.

plications as they can leak whether and when the user opened an email and which software and IP he used.

Until now, the fetching of external URLs in email was only considered to be a privacy threat. In this paper, we abuse backchannels to create plaintext exfiltration channels that allow sending plaintext directly to the attacker. We analyze how an attacker can turn backchannels in email clients to exfiltration channels, and thus obtain victim plaintext messages. We show the existence of backchannels for nearly every email client, ranging from classical HTML resources to OCSP requests and Certificate Revocation lists.

Malleability gadget attacks. Our first attack exploits the construction of obsolete cryptographic primitives, while the second abuses the way how some email clients handle different MIME parts. An important observation for the first attack is that OpenPGP solely uses the Cipher Feedback Mode (CFB) and S/MIME solely uses the Cipher Block Chaining (CBC) mode of operation. Both modes provide *malleability* of plaintexts. This property allows an attacker to reorder, remove or insert ciphertext blocks, or to perform meaningful plaintext modifications without knowing the encryption key. More concretely, he can flip specific bits in the plaintext or even create arbitrary plaintext blocks if he knows parts of the plaintext.

We use the malleability of CBC and CFB to construct so called *malleability gadgets* that allow us to create chosen plaintexts of any length under the assumption that the attacker knows one plaintext block. These malleability gadgets are then used to inject malicious plaintext snippets within the actual plaintext. An ideal malleability gadget attack is possible if the attacker knows one complete plaintext block from the ciphertext, which is 16 bytes for AES. However, fewer known plaintext bytes may also be sufficient, depending on the exfiltration channel that the attacker aims for. Guessing small parts of plaintext is typically feasible since there are hundreds of bytes of static metadata.

With this technique, we were able to defeat the encryption modes used in both S/MIME and PGP. While attacking S/MIME is straightforward, for OpenPGP, we needed to develop more complex exploit techniques upon malleability gadgets because the data is typically compressed before encryption.

Direct exfiltration attacks. Our second attack exploits how different email clients handle emails containing multiple MIME parts. We discovered several attacks variations that solely exploit the complex interaction of HTML together with MIME, S/MIME and OpenPGP in email clients. These cases are straightforward to exploit and do not require any changes of the ciphertext. In the most straightforward example of our attacks, the adversary prepares a plaintext email structure that contains an

 element, whose URL is not closed with quotes.

Contributions. We make the following contributions:

- We introduce the concept of malleability gadgets, which allow an attacker to inject malicious chosen plaintext snippets into the email ciphertext. We describe and apply malleability gadgets for the CBC and CFB modes used in email encryption.
- We analyze all major email clients for backchannels that can be used for the creation of exfiltration channels.
- OpenPGP’s plaintext compression significantly complicates our attack. We describe techniques to create arbitrary plaintexts from specific changes in the compressed plaintext using advanced malleability gadgets.
- We describe practical attacks against major email clients allowing to exfiltrate decrypted emails directly, without ciphertext modifications.
- We discuss medium and long-term countermeasures for email clients and the S/MIME and PGP standards.

Responsible disclosure. We disclosed the vulnerabilities to all affected email vendors and to national CERTs and our findings were confirmed by these bodies.

2 Background

In its simplest form, an email is a text message conforming to the Internet Message Format (IMF) [14]. As the IMF lacks features that are required in the modern Internet, such as the transmission of binary data, it is augmented with *Multipurpose Internet Mail Extension* (MIME) [15] to support transmission of multimedia messages or – in case of OpenPGP and S/MIME – to allow end-to-end encryption of emails.

2.1 End-to-end encrypted email

S/MIME and CMS. The Secure/Multipurpose Internet Mail Extension (S/MIME) is an extension to MIME describing how to send and receive secured MIME data [16]. S/MIME focuses on the MIME-related parts of an email and relies on the *Cryptographic Message Syntax* (CMS) to digitally sign, authenticate, or encrypt arbitrary messages [17]. CMS is a set of binary encoding rules and methods to create secured messages. As it is derived from PKCS#7, the term “PKCS” is found in various headers of secured emails.

Pretty Good Privacy. Phil Zimmerman developed the first version of Pretty Good Privacy (PGP) in 1991 as a means to enable political activists to communicate securely on BBSs, Usenet groups and the early Internet. In the late '90s, the IETF published RFC 2440 describing the OpenPGP format, which has been updated several times. The latest standard is RFC 4880, published in 2007, which describes a variety of methods to encrypt and sign digital data [18].

2.2 Cryptographic basics

In the email context, both S/MIME and PGP use hybrid encryption, in which the sender generates a random session key s that is used to symmetrically encrypt the message m into a cipher text c . The session key s is encrypted with at least two public keys using a public key encryption scheme. The first encryption of s happens with the public key of the sender. Additional encryptions are done using all the public keys of the intended receivers. Thus, s will be encrypted under $n + 1$ different public keys for n recipients of the email. Throughout this paper, we focus on the symmetric encryption.

Encryption modes in OpenPGP and S/MIME. For symmetric encryption of the message m , the standards specify several block ciphers, the most relevant being 3DES and AES. As encryption modes, S/MIME uses *Cipher Block Chaining (CBC)* and OpenPGP uses the *Cipher Feedback Mode (CFB)*. During decryption, both modes produce intermediate values which are XORed (\oplus) with an adjacent ciphertext block to produce the final plaintext block. For CBC, the decryption of C_i into its respective plaintext block is $P_i = dec_s(C_i) \oplus C_{i-1}$. For CFB, it is $P_i = enc_s(C_i) \oplus C_{i+1}$.

Malleability in encryption modes. XOR is a *malleable* operation, which means that flipping a single bit in one of the two operands of XOR results in a bit flip of the final plaintext at the same position. Because XORing with adjacent ciphertext blocks is the final operation in CBC and CFB, precise plaintext manipulations are possible by changing the ciphertext only.

Authenticated encryption Newer encryption schemes will detect modification of the ciphertext and do not output the plaintext in this case. Typically, this is achieved by using *Message Authentication Codes (MACs)* or an *Authenticated Encryption (AE)* scheme. However, both S/MIME and PGP predate these developments and use no authentication at all (S/MIME) or do not strictly commit to the requirements of an AE, which makes them easier to misuse (PGP).

Figure 1: Replacing the URL in the ciphertext blocks (C_{w-1}, C_w) with (C_{i-1}, C_i) to exfiltrate sensitive data.

3 Towards exfiltration attacks

Modern email clients are able to assemble and render various types of content, most notably HTML documents, and HTML provides methods to fetch resources like images and stylesheets from the Internet. Email clients may additionally request other information, for example, to validate the status of a cryptographic certificate. We will refer to all these channels as *backchannels* because they can interact with possibly attacker-controlled servers.

Backchannels in the email context are well-known to be a privacy issue because they allow detecting *if*, *when* and *where* a message has been read and may leak further information such as the user's mail client and operating system. But they are more than that.

In the following sections we show that backchannels can be used to exfiltrate the plaintext of an email after it has been decrypted. The showed methods are directly applicable to S/MIME. For PGP, further requirements must be met, which are discussed in Section 5.

3.1 Block reordering attack

CBC and CFB allow not only precise modifications of the plaintext, but also to reorder ciphertext blocks. With some limitations, changing the order of the ciphertext blocks will effectively also reorder the respective plaintext blocks.

Assume an AES-CBC encrypted HTML email containing an HTML image tag at a known ciphertext pair (C_{w-1}, C_w) . Due to the reordering property, an attacker can replace (C_{w-1}, C_w) with another ciphertext pair (C_{i-1}, C_i) . In effect, the respective plaintext P_i will be reflected in the URL path and the resulting HTTP request will exfiltrate sensitive data a passive MitM attacker can observe (see Figure 1).

3.2 Malleability gadgets

In the previous example, a MitM attacker could exfiltrate those emails that already contained an external HTML image using block reordering. We now relax this constraint and introduce the concept of *malleability gadgets*

Figure 2: Transforming a known plaintext P_i to a chosen plaintext P_c in CBC and CFB.

that allow to inject arbitrary plaintexts into encrypted emails given only a single block of known plaintext.

Definition. Let (C_{i-1}, C_i) be a pair of two ciphertext blocks and P_i the corresponding plaintext block of an CBC encrypted ciphertext. We call $((C_{i-1}, C_i), P_i)$ a *CBC gadget* if P_i is known to an attacker. Accordingly, we call $((C_i, C_{i+1}), P_i)$ of an CFB encrypted ciphertext a *CFB gadget*.

Using CBC gadgets. Given a CBC gadget (see Figure 2 (a)), it is possible to transform P_i into any plaintext P_c by replacing C_{i-1} with $X = C_{i-1} \oplus P_i \oplus P_c$ (see Figure 2 (b)). This comes at a cost as X will be decrypted with an unknown key, resulting in uncontrollable and unknown random bytes in P_{i-1} .

Using CFB gadgets. CFB gadget work similar to CBC gadgets with the difference, that the block after the chosen plaintext block becomes a random block (see Figure 2 (c, d)).

Chosen plaintext and random blocks. A single block of known plaintext is sufficient to inject any amount of chosen plaintext blocks at any block boundary. However, the concatenation of multiple gadgets produces an alternating sequence of chosen plaintext blocks and random blocks. Thus, to create working exfiltration channels, an attacker must deal with these random blocks in a way that they are ignored. One can think of several ways to achieve that. When comments are available within a context, for example via C-style comments `/*` and `*/`, exfiltration channels can easily be constructed by simply commenting out the random blocks. In case no comments are available, characteristics of the underlying data format can be used, for example, that unnamed attributes in HTML are ignored.

4 Attacking S/MIME

In this section we show that S/MIME is vulnerable to CBC gadget attacks, and demonstrate how exfiltration channels can be injected into S/MIME emails.

4.1 S/MIME packet structure

Most clients can either sign, encrypt or sign-then-encrypt messages. Sign-then-encrypt is the preferred wrapping technique when both confidentiality and authenticity are needed. The body of a signed-then-encrypted email consists of two MIME entities, one for signing and one for encryption. The outermost entity – also specified in the email header – is typically *EnvelopedData*. The *EnvelopedData* data structure holds the *RecipientInfos* with multiple encrypted session keys and the *EncryptedContentInfo*. *EncryptedContentInfo* defines which symmetric encryption algorithm was used and finally holds the ciphertext. Decryption of the ciphertext reveals the inner MIME entity holding the plaintext message and its signature. Note that there is no integrity protection.

4.2 Attack description

S/MIME uses the CBC encryption mode to encrypt data, so the CBC gadget from Figure 2 can be used for S/MIME emails. When decrypted, the ciphertext of a signed-then-encrypted email typically starts with `Content-type: multipart/signed`, which reveals enough known-plaintext bytes to fully utilize AES-based CBC gadgets. Therefore, in the case of S/MIME, an attacker can use the first two cipher blocks (IV, C_0) and modify the *IV* to turn P_0 into any chosen plaintext block P_{c_i} .

Injection of exfiltration channels. A slightly simplified version of the attack is shown in Figure 3. The first blocks of a ciphertext whose plaintext we want to exfiltrate are shown in Figure 3 (a). We use (IV, C_0) to construct our CBC gadgets because we know the complete associated plaintext P_0 . Figure 3 (b) shows the *canonical* CBC gadget as it uses $X = IV \oplus P_0$ to set all its plaintext bytes to zero.

We then modify and append multiple CBC gadgets to prepend a chosen ciphertext to the unknown ciphertext blocks (Figure 3 (c)). As a result, we control the plaintext in the first and third block, but the second and fourth block contain random data. The first CBC gadget block P_{c_0} opens an HTML image tag and a meaningless attribute named *ignore*. This attribute is used to consume the random data in the second block such that the random data is not further interpreted. The third block P_{c_1} then starts with the closing quote of the ignored attribute and

Figure 3: Detailed description of the attack on S/MIME. The original ciphertext is shown in (a). (b) is the canonical CBC gadget resulting in an all zero plaintext block. (c) is the modified ciphertext that is sent to the victim.

adds the `src` attribute that contains the domain name from which the email client is supposed to load the image. The fourth plaintext block again contains random data, which is the first part of the path of the image URL. All subsequent blocks contain unknown plaintexts, which now are part of the URL. Finally, when an email client parses this email, the plaintext is sent to the HTTP server defined in P_{c_1} .

Meaningless signatures. One could assume that the decryption of modified ciphertexts would fail because of the digital signature included in the signed-then-encrypted email, but this is not the case, because signature in S/MIME can easily be removed from the multipart/signed mail body [19]. This transforms the signed-then-encrypted email into an encrypted message that has no signature. Of course, a cautious user could detect that this is not an authentic email, but even then, by the time the user detects that, the plaintext would already have been exfiltrated. Signatures can also not become mandatory, because this would hinder anonymous communication. Furthermore, an invalid signature typically does not prevent the display/rendering of a message in email client either. This has historic reasons, as mail gateways could invalidate signatures by changing line-endings in the plaintext, etc.

4.3 Practical exploitation

Exfiltration codes must be designed such that they are ignorant to interleaved random blocks. Although this restriction can be circumvented by careful design of the exfiltration code – recap the usage of the `ignore` attribute – some exfiltration codes may require additional tricks to work in practice.

For example, HTML's `src` attribute, requires the explicit naming of the protocol, e.g. `http://`. Unfortu-

nately, `src="http://` has already 12 bytes, leaving merely enough room for a 4 byte domain. A workaround is to scatter the exfiltration code into multiple HTML elements without breaking its functionality. In case of the `src` attribute, an additional `<base ignore="..." href="http:">` element can be used to globally define the base protocol first.

Emails sent as `text/plain` pose another difficulty. Although there is nothing special about those emails in the context of CBC gadgets, injection of `Content-type: text/html` turned out to be difficult due to restrictions in the MIME headers. An attacker has to apply further tricks such that header parsing will not break when random data is introduced into the header.

5 Attacking OpenPGP

Our exfiltration attacks are not only possible in S/MIME, but also work against OpenPGP. However, there are two additional obstacles: (1) OpenPGP uses compression by default and (2) *Modification Detection Codes (MDC)* are used for integrity protection.

Compression. In the context of malleability gadgets, compression makes exploitation more difficult, because the compressed plaintext is harder to guess. Similar to S/MIME, PGP emails also contain known headers and plaintext blocks, for example, `Content-Type: multipart/mixed`, but after compression is applied, the resulting plaintext may vastly differ per mail.

The difficulty here is to guess a certain amount of compressed plaintext bytes in order to fully utilize the CFB gadget technique. Not knowing enough compressed plaintext bytes is hardly a countermeasure, but makes practical exploitation a lot harder.

Since an attack was published against this integrity protection mechanism [22], its interpretation is discouraged [18], and the two bytes are ignored. They depict the beginning of the first real plaintext block and the SE and SEIP packet types treat them differently.

5.3 Defeating deflate

OpenPGP utilizes the *deflate* algorithm [23] to compress LD packets before encrypting them. It is based on LZ77 (specifically LZSS) and Huffman Coding. Although the exact details are not important for this paper, it is important to note that a single message may be partitioned, such that different *modes of compression* can be used for different segments of the message.

Modes of compression. The standard defines three modes of compression: uncompressed, compressed with fixed Huffman trees, and compressed with dynamic Huffman trees. It is specified by a header prepended to each segment. A single OpenPGP CD packet can contain multiple compressed or uncompressed segments.²

Backreferences. Typically, a full message is wrapped inside a single compressed segment. Then, the algorithm applies a search for *text fragment* repetitions of certain length within the boundaries of a *sliding window*. If a repetition is found, it is replaced with a shorter pointer to its previous occurrence.

For example, the text `How much wood could a woodchuck chuck is shortened to How much wood could a <-13, 4>chuck <-6, 5>`. In reality, the deflate algorithm encodes backreferences as small bit strings to achieve a higher compression level. The backreference strings are inserted into a Huffman tree that is placed before the compressed text. During the decompression process, the algorithm uses the Huffman tree to restore these patterns.

Uncompressed segments. In addition to compressed segments, the deflate data format also specifies uncompressed segments. These segments are also used during the search for repetitions, but, in contrast to compressed segments, may contain arbitrary data. This is an important observation, because it allows us to work around the limited amount of known plaintext.

Dynamic and fixed Huffman trees. Starting from around 90 to 100 bytes of plaintext, deflate uses a dynamic Huffman tree that is serialized to bytes and forms the start of the deflate data. Dynamic Huffman trees

²RFC 1951 speaks of “blocks”. We change the terminology to “segments” for better readability.

change substantially and are difficult to predict for partly unknown plaintexts. For shorter texts, fixed Huffman trees are used. They are statically defined in [23] and not located in the data. In the following sections, we assume fixed Huffman trees to outline the attack.

5.3.1 Creating a CFB gadget

The first encrypted block seems most promising, because it consists of OpenPGP packet metadata and compression headers.

By exploiting *backreferences* in the compression algorithm we are able to use only 11 bytes long malleability gadgets. These backreferences allow us to reference and concatenate arbitrary blocks of data and thus create exfiltration channels more precisely. Therefore, instead of trying to work around the compression, we use it to precisely inject our exfiltration codes in compressed form.

5.3.2 Exfiltrating compressed plaintexts

Assume we are in possession of an OpenPGP SEIP packet which decrypts to a compressed plaintext. We know one decrypted block which allows us to construct a malleability gadget and thus arbitrary number of chosen plaintexts. Our goal is to construct a ciphertext which decrypts to a compressed packet. Its decompression leads to an exfiltration of the target plaintext.

A simplified attack is shown in Figure 5 and can be performed as follows. Using our malleability gadget we first create three ciphertext block pairs (C_i, C_{i+1}) which decrypt into useful text fragments (P_{c0}, P_{c1}, P_{c2}) . The first text fragment represents an OpenPGP packet structure which encodes a CD packet (which is encoded as `0xaf` in OpenPGP) containing a LD packet (encoded as `0xa3`). The latter two text fragments contain an exfiltration channel, for example, `
18 --BOUNDARY--

```

(a) Attacker-prepared email received by email client.

```

1

```

(b) HTML code after decryption as interpreted by the client.

```

1 http://efail.de/Secret%20MeetingTomorrow%209pm

```

(c) HTTP request sent by mail client

Figure 6: Malicious email structure and missing context boundaries force the client to decrypt the ciphertext and leak the plaintext using the `<img>` element.

other clients our attacks require user interaction. For example, in Thunderbird and Postbox we can completely redress the UI with CSS and trick the user into submitting the plaintext with an HTML form if he clicks somewhere into the message. Note that thanks to the MIME structure the attacker can include several ciphertexts into one email and exfiltrate their plaintexts at once. For Thunderbird this security issue is present since v0.1 (2003).

## 7 Exfiltration channels in email clients

Backchannels in email clients are known as privacy risks, but there is no comprehensive overview yet. We performed an analysis of existing backchannels by systematically testing 48 clients and give the complete results in Appendix B. Note that 13 of the tested clients do either not support encryption at all or we could not get the OpenPGP or S/MIME modules to work and therefore could not test whether backchannels can be used for exfiltration. This distinction is important because some email clients behave differently for encrypted and unencrypted messages. For example, HTML content that can be used to load external images in unencrypted mails is usually not interpreted for deprecated PGP/*INLINE* messages. On the other hand, for three clients we were able to bypass remote content blocking simply by encrypting the HTML email containing a simple `` tag.

| OS        | Client          | S/MIME | PGP  |      |    |
|-----------|-----------------|--------|------|------|----|
|           |                 |        | -MDC | +MDC | SE |
| Windows   | Outlook 2007    | ∠      | ∠    | ∠    | ✓  |
|           | Outlook 2010    | ∠      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Outlook 2013    | ⊥      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Outlook 2016    | ⊥      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Win. 10 Mail    | ∠      | -    | -    | -  |
|           | Win. Live Mail  | ∠      | -    | -    | -  |
|           | The Bat!        | ⊥      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Postbox         | ∠      | ∠    | ∠    | ∠  |
|           | eM Client       | ∠      | ✓    | ∠    | ✓  |
| IBM Notes | ∠               | -      | -    | -    |    |
| Linux     | Thunderbird     | ∠      | ∠    | ∠    | ∠  |
|           | Evolution       | ∠      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Trojita         | ∠      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | KMail           | ⊥      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Claws           | ✓      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Mutt            | ✓      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
| macOS     | Apple Mail      | ∠      | ∠    | ∠    | ∠  |
|           | MailMate        | ∠      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Airmail         | ∠      | ∠    | ∠    | ∠  |
| iOS       | Mail App        | ∠      | -    | -    | -  |
|           | Canary Mail     | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
| Android   | K-9 Mail        | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | R2Mail2         | ∠      | ✓    | ∠    | ✓  |
|           | MailDroid       | ∠      | ✓    | ∠    | ✓  |
|           | Nine            | ∠      | -    | -    | -  |
| Webmail   | United Internet | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Mailbox.org     | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | ProtonMail      | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Mailfence       | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | GMail           | ∠      | -    | -    | -  |
| Webapp    | Roundcube       | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ∠  |
|           | Horde IMP       | ⊥      | ✓    | ∠    | ∠  |
|           | AfterLogic      | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Rainloop        | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |
|           | Mailpile        | -      | ✓    | ✓    | ✓  |

∠ Exfiltration (no user interaction)    ✓ No exfiltration channel  
⊥ Exfiltration (with user interaction)    - Encryption not supported

Table 4: Exfiltration channels for various email clients for S/MIME, PGP SEIP with stripped MDC (-MDC), PGP SEIP with wrong MDC (+MDC), and PGP SE packets.

Table 4 shows the 35 remaining clients. An attacker can exploit 23 S/MIME email clients out of which eight require either a MitM attacker or user interaction like clicking on a link or explicitly allowing external images. 17 S/MIME clients allow off-path exfiltration channels with no user interaction.

From the 35 email clients, 28 support OpenPGP and 10 allow off-path exfiltration channels with no user interaction. Five clients allow SEIP ciphertexts with stripped MDC and ignore wrong MDCs if they exist. Six clients support SE ciphertexts. Three clients – which show OpenPGP messages as plain text only – are secure against automated backchannels, but are still vulnerable to backchannels that require more complex user interaction.

## 7.1 Web content in email clients

**HTML.** The most prominent form of HTML content are images. Of the tested 48 email clients, 13 load external images by default. For 10 of them, this can be turned off whereas three clients have no option to block remote content. All other clients block external images by default or explicitly ask the user before downloading.

We analyzed all HTML elements that could potentially bypass the blocking filter and trigger a backchannel using a comprehensive list of HTML4, HTML5 and non-standard HTML elements that allow including URIs. For each element-attribute combination, links were built using a variety of well-known<sup>4</sup> and unofficial<sup>5</sup> URI schemes based on the assumption that `http://` links may be blacklisted by a mail client while others might be allowed. We added specific link/meta tags in the HTML header. In addition, we tested against the vectors from the *Email Privacy Tester*<sup>6</sup> project and the *Cure53 HTTPLeaks*<sup>7</sup> repository. This extensive list of test-cases allowed us to bypass external content blocking in 22 email clients.

**Cascading Style Sheets (CSS).** Most mail clients allow CSS declarations to be included in HTML emails. Based on the CSS2 and CSS3 standards we assembled an extensive list of properties that allow included URIs, like `background-image: url("http://efail.de")`. These allowed bypassing remote content blocking on 11 clients.

**JavaScript.** We used well-known Cross Site Scripting test vectors<sup>8,9</sup> and placed them in various header fields like `Subject:` as well as in the mail body. We identified five mail clients which are prone to JavaScript execution, allowing the construction of particularly flexible backchannels.

## 7.2 S/MIME specific backchannels

**OCSP requests.** Mail clients can use the Online Certificate Status Protocol (OCSP) to check the validity of X.509 certificates that are included in S/MIME signatures. OCSP works as follows: the client decrypts the email, parses the certificate and obtains the URL of the OCSP-responder. The client then sends the serial number of the certificate via HTTP POST to the responder

<sup>4</sup><https://www.w3.org/wiki/UriSchemes>

<sup>5</sup><https://github.com/Munter/schemes>

<sup>6</sup><https://www.emailprivacytester.com/>

<sup>7</sup><https://github.com/cure53/HTTPLeaks>

<sup>8</sup>[https://www.owasp.org/index.php/XSS\\_Filter\\_Evasion\\_Cheat\\_Sheet](https://www.owasp.org/index.php/XSS_Filter_Evasion_Cheat_Sheet)

<sup>9</sup><http://html5sec.org>

and obtains a data structure with status information about the certificate.

Using this channel for data exfiltration requires replacing the URL ciphertext blocks with other ciphertext blocks. In typical scenarios this is complicated by two factors: One, the OCSP-responder's URL is part of a larger base64 encoded data structure. Therefore, an attacker must be careful not to destroy the base64-decoding process by carefully selecting or masking the plaintext. Two, if a valid certificate chain is used, the OCSP-responder's URL is cryptographically signed which makes this backchannel unusable as long as the signature is properly checked. Eleven clients performed OCSP requests for valid certificates from a trusted CA.

**CRL requests.** Similar to OCSP, Certificate Revocation Lists (CRLs) are used to obtain recent status information about a certificate. Unlike OCSP, a CRL is periodically requested and contains a list of multiple serial numbers of revoked certificates. Requesting the list involves an HTTP request to the server holding the CRL and the CRL backchannel is very similar to the OCSP backchannel. Ten clients performed CRL requests for valid certificates from a trusted CA, one client even connected to an untrusted, attacker-controlled web server.

**Intermediate certificates.** S/MIME is built around the concept of hierarchical trust and requires following a certificate chain back to a trusted root. If the certificate is incomplete and intermediate certificates are missing, the chain can not be verified. To remedy this, a CA may augment certificates with an URL to the next link in the chain. A client can query this URL to obtain the missing certificates. These requests for intermediate certificates can be used as a backchannel. Like the backchannels via OCSP and CRL requests, this is made difficult by the base64 encoding. However, the signature can only be verified *after* the intermediate certificate was obtained. This makes exploitation of this channel much easier. Seven clients requested intermediate certificates from an attacker-controlled LDAP and/or web server.

### 7.3 OpenPGP specific backchannels

An email client receiving a PGP-signed message may try to automatically download the corresponding public key. There are various protocols to achieve this, for example DANE [24], HKP [25] or LDAP [26] [27]. We observed one client trying to obtain the public key for a given key ID. This can potentially be abused by malleability gadgets to leak four bytes of plaintext. We also applied 33 PGP-related email headers that refer to public keys (e.g. X-PGP-Key: URI), but none of the tested

clients performed a request to the given URL, therefore the issue is only relevant to a MitM attacker.

### 7.4 External attachments

The `message/external-body` content type allows references to external resources as MIME parts instead of directly including within the mail. This is a known technique to bypass virus scanners running on a mail gateway. However, there are various proprietary variants of this header, for which one email client automatically performed a DNS request for the external attachment's hostname. It is noteworthy that this was done automatically, the email did not have to be explicitly opened.

### 7.5 Email security gateways

Email security gateways are typically used in large enterprises to secure the outgoing communication with S/MIME or OpenPGP. This ensures that employees do not have to install any extensions or generate keys, and that their emails are automatically encrypted and decrypted.

Our attacks are applicable to email security gateways as well. In fact, preventing the showed attacks in these scenarios could be even more challenging, especially for the MIME-related issues. The reason is that a gateway is only used to decrypt the incoming emails and has no knowledge of the email processing clients.

We were not able to systematically analyze security gateways as they are not easily accessible. Nevertheless, we had a chance to test two appliances. The configuration of the first one was insecure and we could find a direct exfiltration exploit. The second gateway was configured correctly and we were not able to find any direct exploits in the limited time we had for the evaluation.

## 8 Mitigations

Backchannels are critical, because they provide a way to *instantly* obtain the plaintext of an email. Reliably blocking *all* backchannels, including those not based on HTML, would prevent all the attacks *as presented*. However, it does not fix the underlying vulnerability in the S/MIME and OpenPGP standards. In a broader scenario, an attacker could also inject binary attachments or modify already attached ones, such that exfiltration is done later even if no email client is involved. Therefore, blocking network requests is only a short-term solution. In the following section we present long-term mitigations which require updating the standards.

## 8.1 Countering direct exfiltration attacks

**Same origin policy for email.** The complexity of HTML, CSS and MIME makes it possible to mix encrypted and plaintext contents. If an exfiltration channel is available, this can lead to direct leaks of decrypted plaintexts, independently of whether the ciphertext is authenticated or not. In web scenarios, a typical protection against these kinds of attacks is the same origin policy [28]. Similar protection mechanisms could be applied in email scenarios as well. These should enforce that email parts with different security properties are not combined.

However, this mitigation is hard to enforce in every scenario. For example, email gateways typically used in companies process encrypted emails and forward the plain data to email clients used by the employees. Email clients have no knowledge whether the original message was encrypted or not. In such scenarios this countermeasure must be combined with different techniques. An effective mitigation for an email gateway would be to display only the first email body part and convert further body parts into attachments.

## 8.2 Countering malleability gadget attacks

The S/MIME standard does not provide any effective security measures countering our attacks. OpenPGP provides Message Modification Codes and we could observe several OpenPGP implementations that were not vulnerable to our attacks because they dropped ciphertexts with invalid MDCs. Unfortunately, the OpenPGP standard is not clear about handling MDC failures. The standard only vaguely states that any failures in the MDC check “MUST be treated as a security problem” and “SHOULD be reported to the user” [18] but lacks a definition on how to deal with security problems. Furthermore, the standard still supports SE packets which offer no integrity protection. From this perspective, the security vulnerabilities observed in GnuPG and Enigmail are standard-conforming, as GnuPG returns an error code and prints out a specific error message. Our experiments showed that different clients deal differently with MDC failures (see Table 4).

In the long-term, updating the S/MIME and OpenPGP standards is inevitable to meet modern cryptographic best practices and introduce authenticated encryption algorithms.

**Authenticated encryption (AE).** Our attack would be prevented if the email client detects changes in the ciphertext during decryption *and* prevents it from being displayed. On a first thought, making an AE block cipher such as AES-GCM the default, would prevent the

attack.

Although CMS defines an *AuthenticatedData* type [29], S/MIME’s current specification does not. There were efforts to introduce authenticated encryption in OpenPGP which is, however, expired [30].

By introducing these algorithms, the standard would need to address backwards compatibility attacks and handling of streaming-based decryption.

**Solving backwards compatibility problems.** In a backwards compatibility attack an attacker takes a secure authenticated ciphertext (e.g., AES-GCM) and forces the receiver to use a weak encryption method (e.g., AES-CBC) [31]. To prevent these attacks, usage of different keys for different cryptographic primitives has to be enforced. For example, the decrypted key can be used as an input into a key derivation function KDF together with an algorithm identifier. This would enforce different keys for different algorithms:

$$k_{\text{AES-CBC}} = \text{KDF}(k, \text{“AES-CBC”}) \quad (1)$$

$$k_{\text{AES-GCM}} = \text{KDF}(k, \text{“AES-GCM”}) \quad (2)$$

Although an email client could use S/MIME’s *capabilities list* to promote more secure ciphers in every signature, an attacker can still forward emails she obtained in the past. The email client may then (a) process the old email and stay susceptible to exfiltration attacks or (2) do not process the email and break interoperability.

**Streaming-based decryption.** OpenPGP uses streaming, i.e. it passes on plaintext parts during decryption if the ciphertext is large. This feature collides with our request for AE ciphers because most AE ciphers also support streaming. In the event that the ciphertext was modified, it will pass on already decrypted plaintext, along with an error code at the end. If these plaintext parts are interpreted, exfiltration channels may arise despite using an AE cipher. We think it is safe to turn off streaming in the email context because the size of email ciphertexts is limited and can be handled by modern computers. Otherwise, if the ciphertext size is a concern, the email should be split into chunks which are encrypted and authenticated so that no streaming is needed. A cryptographic approach to solve this problem would be to use a mode of operation which does not allow for decrypting the ciphertext before its authenticity is validated. For example, AES-SIV could be used [32]. Note that AES-SIV works in two phases and thus it does not offer such performance as e.g., AES-GCM.

## 9 Related work

In 2000 Katz and Schneier described a chosen-ciphertext attack [33] that *blinds* an uncompressed ciphertext, which they send in a spoofed email to the victim. They then hope that the victim replies to the email with the blinded ciphertext, that they can then unblind. This attack requires a cooperating victim and does not work against compressed plaintexts.

In 2001 Davis described “surreptitious forwarding” attacks and their applicability to S/MIME, PKCS#7, MOSS, PEM, PGP, and XML [34] in which an attacker can re-sign or re-encrypt the original email and forward it onto a third person.

In 2002 Perrin presented a downgrade attack, which removes the integrity protection turning a SEIP into a SE data packet [20]. In 2015, Magazinius showed that this downgrade attack is applicable in practice [21].

In 2005 Mister and Zuccherato described an adaptive-chosen-ciphertext attack [22] exploiting OpenPGP’s integrity *quick check*. The attacker need  $2^{15}$  queries to decrypt two plaintext bytes per block. The attack requires a high number of queries, which makes the attack unpractical for email encryption.

Strenzke [19] improved one of Davis’ attacks and noted that an attacker can strip a signature and re-sign the encrypted email with his private key. He sends the email to the victim who hopefully responds with an email including the decrypted ciphertext.

Many attacks abuse CBC malleability property to create chosen-ciphertext attacks [35–38]. Practical attacks have been shown against IPsec [39, 40], SSH [41, 42], TLS [43–46], or XML Encryption [47]. Overall, the attacker uses the server as an oracle. This is not possible in typical OpenPGP and S/MIME scenarios, since users are unlikely to open many emails without getting suspicious. Some of these attacks exploit that with CBC it is also possible to encrypt arbitrary plaintext blocks or bytes [38, 40, 47]. For example, Rizzo and Duong described how to turn a *decryption oracle into an encryption oracle*. They used their CBC-R technique to compute correct headers and issue malicious JSF view states [38].

In 2005, Fruwirth, the author of the Linux Unified Key Setup (luks), wrote a compendium of attacks and insecure properties of CBC [48] in the hard disk encryption context. Later in 2013, Lell presented a practical exploit for CBC malleability against a Ubuntu 12.04 installation that is encrypted using luks [49] with CBC. An attack very similar to Lell’s was described in 2016 in the Owncloud server side encryption module [50].

In 2017 Cure53 analyzed the security of Enigmail [51]. The report shows that surreptitious forwarding is still possible and that it is possible to spoof OpenPGP

signatures.

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## A Unsuccessful backchannel tests

We pursued further tests which were not successful but are documented here for the sake of completeness.

**Spam datasets.** We checked whether spammers may already be aware of bypasses for remote content blocking in email clients and analyzed two large spam datasets<sup>10,11</sup> containing over ten millions of spam emails altogether ranging from 1997 to 2018. However, we found that spammers do not use or are not aware of bypasses for content blocking as they only included well-known technique to trace if an email is actually read.

**Generic email headers.** There are various standardized and proprietary email headers<sup>12</sup> which allow to include URIs. Furthermore, we used various public email datasets to compile a list of 9,400 mail headers which contain URLs. We tested those headers against all email clients, but none triggered with the exception of external attachments mentioned in Section 7.4

**Anti-spoofing headers.** We included email headers to fight spam (SPF, DKIM), however the triggered DNS requests at the MTA level, not when mail was opened in the MUA. It is however noteworthy that two email clients performed a DNS lookups for the hostname part of the sender email address at the time the mail was opened. although this is a privacy issue, we cannot use it to for exfiltration because the DNS request was no longer triggered for `From:` header within the encrypted part of the message.

**Message disposition notification.** We identified seven standardized and proprietary email headers which request a confirmation mail attesting that the message has been read. Two mail clients automatically send confirmation emails which has a privacy impact but cannot be used as an exfiltration channel because the mail was not triggered if the message disposition notification header was within the encrypted part. All other clients do not support the feature or explicitly ask the user before sending a message disposition notifications.

**File preview.** Some email clients try to generate a preview for attached files. We prepared specially-crafted PDF, SVG, vCard and vCalendar files which contain hyperlinks, trigger a connection or execute JavaScript when opened. However in the previewed version none of these actions was taken for any of the tested clients.

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<sup>10</sup><http://untroubled.org/spam/>

<sup>11</sup><http://artinvoice.hu/spams/>

<sup>12</sup><https://www.iana.org/assignments/message-headers/message-headers.xhtml>

## B Backchannel analysis

This section presents the table summarizing our results on backchannels in email clients.

|           |                                 | Support |              | Backchannels |                                       |               |
|-----------|---------------------------------|---------|--------------|--------------|---------------------------------------|---------------|
|           |                                 | S/MIME  | PGP          | Email        | HTML/CSS/JS                           | PKI           |
| Windows   | Outlook 2007 (12.0.4518.1014)   | native  | GPG4win      |              | $H_{15} P_1$                          | $I_1 I_2 I_3$ |
|           | Outlook 2010 (14.0.7190.5000)   | native  | GPG4win      |              | $P_1$                                 | $I_2 I_3$     |
|           | Outlook 2013 (15.0.4989.1000)   | native  | GPG4win      |              |                                       | $I_2 I_3$     |
|           | Outlook 2016 (16.0.4266.1001)   | native  | GPG4Win      |              |                                       | $I_2 I_3$     |
|           | Win. 8 Mail (17.4.9600.16384)   | n/a     | n/a          |              | $+ H_1 H_6$                           |               |
|           | Win. 10 Mail (17.8730.21865.0)  | native  | n/a          |              | $+$                                   |               |
|           | Win. Live Mail (16.4.3528.0331) | native  | n/a          |              | $H_{17}$                              | $I_1 I_2$     |
|           | The Bat! (8.2.0)                | native  | GnuPG        | $E_1$        |                                       |               |
|           | Postbox (5.0.20)                | native  | Enigmail     |              | $P_3$                                 | $I_2$         |
|           | eM Client (7.1.31849.0)         | native  | native       | $E_3$        | $J_3$                                 | $I_1 I_2$     |
|           | IBM Notes (9.0.1)               | native  | n/a          |              | $H_{13} H_{16} P_2 J_1$               |               |
|           | Foxmail (7.2.8)                 | n/a     | n/a          |              | $*$                                   |               |
|           | Pegasus Mail (4.72.572)         | n/a     | PMPGP        | $E_1$        | $H_{14} P_2 P_4$                      |               |
| Linux     | Thunderbird (52.5.2)            | native  | Enigmail     |              | $H_2$                                 | $I_2$         |
|           | Evolution (3.22.6)              | native  | GnuPG        |              | $H_3$                                 |               |
|           | Trojita (0.7-278)               | native  | GnuPG        |              | $H_3$                                 | $I_3$         |
|           | KMail (5.2.3)                   | native  | GnuPG        |              |                                       | $I_3$         |
|           | Claws (3.14.1)                  | plugin  | GPG plugin   |              |                                       | $I_3$         |
|           | Mutt (1.7.2)                    | native  | GnuPG        |              |                                       | $I_3$         |
| macOS     | Apple Mail (11.2)               | native  | GPGTools     | $E_2$        | $+$                                   | $I_1 I_2 I_3$ |
|           | MailMate (1.10)                 | native  | GPGTools     |              | $H_3$                                 | $I_1 I_2 I_3$ |
|           | Airmail (3.5.3)                 | plugin  | GPG-PGP      |              | $+ H_{10} H_{11} H_{14}$              |               |
| iOS       | Mail App (11.2.2)               | native  | n/a          |              | $+$                                   | $I_1$         |
|           | Canary Mail (1.17)              | n/a     | native       | $E_4$        | $+$                                   |               |
|           | Outlook (2.56.0)                | n/a     | n/a          |              | $*$                                   |               |
| Android   | K-9 Mail (5.403)                | n/a     | OpenKeychain |              |                                       |               |
|           | R2Mail2 (2.30)                  | native  | native       |              | $H_{10} J_2$                          |               |
|           | MailDroid (4.81)                | Flipdog | Flipdog      |              | $H_4 H_5 H_{14} H_{15} J_2$           |               |
|           | Nine (4.1.3a)                   | native  | n/a          |              | $K_2 H_4 H_5 H_{14} H_{15} J_1$       |               |
| Webmail   | GMX, Web.de, ...                | n/a     | Mailvelope   |              | $+ K_1 C_7 C_8 C_9$                   |               |
|           | Mailbox.org                     | n/a     | Mailvelope   |              | $K_1 C_9$                             |               |
|           | Hushmail                        | n/a     | native       |              |                                       |               |
|           | ProtonMail                      | n/a     | OpenPGP.js   |              | $H_3 H_4 H_{12} H_{14} H_{15} C_1$    |               |
|           | Mailfence                       | native  | OpenPGP.js   |              | $H_8 C_5 C_{12} C_{15}$               | $I_3$         |
|           | GMail                           | native  | n/a          |              | $+$                                   |               |
|           | Outlook.com                     | native  | n/a          |              | $+$                                   |               |
|           | iCloud Mail                     | n/a     | n/a          |              | $+$                                   |               |
|           | Yahoo Mail                      | n/a     | n/a          |              | $C_5 C_{11}$                          |               |
|           | FastMail                        | n/a     | n/a          |              | $+$                                   |               |
|           | Mail.Ru                         | n/a     | n/a          |              | $*$                                   |               |
|           | Zoho Mail                       | n/a     | n/a          |              | $H_9 C_{12} P_1$                      |               |
| Webapp    | Roundcube (1.3.4)               | native  | Enigma       |              | $H_7 C_3$                             |               |
|           | AfterLogic (7.7.9)              | plugin  | OpenPGP.js   |              | $H_4 C_2 C_{10} C_{13} C_{14} C_{16}$ |               |
|           | Rainloop (1.11.3)               | n/a     | OpenPGP.js   |              | $C_4 C_{13} C_{14}$                   |               |
|           | Mailpile (1.0.0rc2)             | n/a     | GnuPG        |              | $\#$                                  |               |
| Groupware | Exchange OWA (15.1.1034.32)     | native  | n/a          |              |                                       | $I_1 I_2$     |
|           | GroupWise (14.2.2)              | native  | n/a          |              | $H_9 C_2 C_5 C_{11} C_{12}$           |               |
|           | Horde (5.2.22/IMP 6.2.21)       | native  | GnuPG        |              |                                       | $I_4$         |

Backchannel to arbitrary URI
  Backchannel to fixed URI

Table 5: Backchannels for various email clients. (Legend on next page.)

| <b>Legend</b>                                                 |                                                                                            |
|---------------------------------------------------------------|--------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| +                                                             | Remote images are loaded by default but this can be deactivated                            |
| *                                                             | Remote images are loaded by default and it cannot be deactivated                           |
| #                                                             | Remote images are loaded through prefetching in modern browsers                            |
| <b>PKI requests</b>                                           |                                                                                            |
| <i>I</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         | Request for intermediate S/MIME certificate are performed to an attacker-controlled URI    |
| <i>I</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | OCSP requests to a fixed CA URL are performed for valid/trusted S/MIME signed emails       |
| <i>I</i> <sub>3</sub>                                         | CRL requests to a fixed CA URL are performed for valid/trusted S/MIME signed emails        |
| <i>I</i> <sub>4</sub>                                         | HKP requests to keyserver are performed to retrieve public keys for PGP signed emails      |
| <b>Encrypted emails</b>                                       |                                                                                            |
| <i>K</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         | Remote images are loaded automatically if the mail is PGP/MIME encrypted                   |
| <i>K</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | Remote images are loaded automatically if the mail is S/MIME encrypted                     |
| <b>HTML attributes (bypasses for remote content blocking)</b> |                                                                                            |
| <i>H</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         | <html manifest="http://efail.de"></html>                                                   |
| <i>H</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | <link href="http://efail.de" rel="preconnect">                                             |
| <i>H</i> <sub>3</sub>                                         | <meta http-equiv="x-dns-prefetch-control" content="on"><a href="http://efail.de"></a>      |
| <i>H</i> <sub>4</sub>                                         | <meta http-equiv="refresh" content="1; url=http://efail.de">                               |
| <i>H</i> <sub>5</sub>                                         | <base href="http://efail.de"><iframe src="x">                                              |
| <i>H</i> <sub>6</sub>                                         |                                                              |
| <i>H</i> <sub>7</sub>                                         | <image src="http://efail.de">                                                              |
| <i>H</i> <sub>8</sub>                                         | <svg><image href="http://efail.de"/></svg>                                                 |
| <i>H</i> <sub>9</sub>                                         | <input type="image" src="http://efail.de"/>                                                |
| <i>H</i> <sub>10</sub>                                        | <audio src="http://efail.de">                                                              |
| <i>H</i> <sub>11</sub>                                        | <video src="http://efail.de">                                                              |
| <i>H</i> <sub>12</sub>                                        | <video poster="http://efail.de">                                                           |
| <i>H</i> <sub>13</sub>                                        | <script src="http://efail.de">                                                             |
| <i>H</i> <sub>14</sub>                                        | <embed src="http://efail.de"></embed>                                                      |
| <i>H</i> <sub>15</sub>                                        | <object data="http://efail.de"></object>                                                   |
| <i>H</i> <sub>16</sub>                                        | <object codebase="http://efail.de"></object>                                               |
| <i>H</i> <sub>17</sub>                                        | <p style="background-image:url(1)"></p><object><embed src="http://efail.de">               |
| <b>CSS properties (bypasses for remote content blocking)</b>  |                                                                                            |
| <i>C</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         | <style>@import url('http://efail.de');</style>                                             |
| <i>C</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | <style>body {background-image: url('http://efail.de');}</style>                            |
| <i>C</i> <sub>3</sub>                                         | <style>body {background-image: \75 \72 \6C ('http://efail.de');}</style>                   |
| <i>C</i> <sub>4</sub>                                         | <style>body {shape-outside: url(http://efail.de);}</style>                                 |
| <i>C</i> <sub>5</sub>                                         | <div style="background-image: url('http://efail.de')">                                     |
| <i>C</i> <sub>6</sub>                                         | <div style="background-image: -moz-image-rect(url('https://efail.de'), 85%, 5%, 5%, 5%);"> |
| <i>C</i> <sub>7</sub>                                         | <style>body {background: #aaa url('http://efail.de');}</style>                             |
| <i>C</i> <sub>8</sub>                                         | <div style="background: #aaa url('http://efail.de')">                                      |
| <i>C</i> <sub>9</sub>                                         | <style>ul {list-style: url('http://efail.de');}</style><ul><li>item</li></ul>              |
| <i>C</i> <sub>10</sub>                                        | <ul style="list-style: url('http://efail.de');"></ul>                                      |
| <i>C</i> <sub>11</sub>                                        | <style>ul {list-style-image: url('http://efail.de');}</style><ul><li>item</li></ul>        |
| <i>C</i> <sub>12</sub>                                        | <ul style="list-style-image: url('http://efail.de')"></ul>                                 |
| <i>C</i> <sub>13</sub>                                        | <div style="border-image: url('http://efail.de');">                                        |
| <i>C</i> <sub>14</sub>                                        | <div style="border-image-source: url('http://efail.de');">                                 |
| <i>C</i> <sub>15</sub>                                        | <div style="cursor: url('http://efail.de') 5 5, auto;">                                    |
| <i>C</i> <sub>16</sub>                                        | <svg/><svg><rect cursor="url(http://efail.de), auto"/></svg>                               |
| <b>URI schemes (bypasses for remote content blocking)</b>     |                                                                                            |
| <i>P</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         |                                                                      |
| <i>P</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         |                                                               |
| <i>P</i> <sub>3</sub>                                         |                                                               |
| <i>P</i> <sub>4</sub>                                         |                                                                |
| <b>JavaScript (bypasses for remote content blocking)</b>      |                                                                                            |
| <i>J</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         | <script>...</script>                                                                       |
| <i>J</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | <object data="javascript:..."></object>                                                    |
| <i>J</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | <svg><style>'<body/onload="..."></script>                                                  |
| <b>Email headers</b>                                          |                                                                                            |
| <i>E</i> <sub>1</sub>                                         | X-Confirm-Reading-To: user@efail.de                                                        |
| <i>E</i> <sub>2</sub>                                         | Remote-Attachment-Url: http://efail.de                                                     |
| <i>E</i> <sub>3</sub>                                         | From: user@efail.de (HTTP request for favicon)                                             |
| <i>E</i> <sub>4</sub>                                         | From: user@efail.de (DNS request to hostname)                                              |